

Press Release

November 2025

The PQ-NEXT EU project has been launched, aiming to smooth and secure the migration to the post-quantum cryptography era

The PQ-NEXT (Post-Quantum Networks for Energy-eXfficient Transitions) project held its first online kick-off meeting on Tuesday, 18th November 2025. By bringing together 17 highly experienced partners from across the European Union, including **Greece, Spain, Germany, Italy, Poland, and Bulgaria**, the PQ-NEXT consortium is dedicated to securing the smooth transition to the post-quantum cryptography era, coordinated by the National Centre for Scientific Research “Demokritos”.

By developing a comprehensive migration framework that analyses and models scenarios for the transition to post-quantum cryptographic (PQC) standards and by providing tailored migration plans, the PQ-NEXT project will enable a smooth, secure transition while minimising the risks associated with the new post-quantum cryptography era. The project’s large-scale pilots in **finance, critical infrastructure, telecommunications, and digital identities**, through the selected use of digital twinning, will validate the solutions developed.

PQ-NEXT is the continuation of the Horizon Europe project [PQ-REACT: Post Quantum Cryptography Framework for Energy Aware Contexts](#). All the knowledge generated will serve as the basis for PQ-NEXT to secure the smooth transition to the post-quantum era in the EU and beyond.

The Team

At the center of PQ-NEXT is a unified team whose expertise spans across **PQC, Context Agility, QKD, Quantum Processing Applications, Legal/Risk Assessment, Standardisation and Communication**. The project is coordinated by the [National Center For Scientific Research "Demokritos"](#), including [Fraunhofer Gesellschaft](#), [Universidad Politecnica De Madrid](#), [Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna di Pisa](#), [Athena Research Center](#), [AGH University of Kraków](#), [Hochschule RheinMain](#), [Indra](#), [Telefónica Innovación Digital](#), [Motor Oil](#), [Infili Technologies SA](#), [Caixabank](#), [AUSTRALO](#), [Sploro](#), [SmartLex](#), [AFCEA Sofia Chapter](#), [Dimos Egaleo](#).

For more information, questions and collaborations, please contact:
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